

The Addition of Halogens to Isoprene and Chloroprene

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The reactions between bromine and chloroprene (2-chloro-1,3-butadiene), bromine and isoprene (2-methyl-1,3-butadiene) and chlorine and isoprene have been investigated.

The reaction between bromine and chloroprene goes essentially by 1, 4-addition to give *trans*-2-chloro-1, 4-dibromo-2-butene with a small amount of 1, 2- and 3, 4-addition as indicated by lithium aluminum hydride reduction of the reaction products. Similar analysis of the reaction products from bromine and isoprene is complicated by allylic rearrangement of the 1, 2- and 3, 4-addition products to the 1, 4-addition product and also by the fact that the lithium aluminum hydride reduction of both of these addition products could give 2-methyl-2-butene, the reduction product of the 1, 4-addition compound. The products of the reduction consist only of those arising from the 1, 2-, 3, 4- and 1, 4-addition compounds. No. monobromo diene was obtained.

The reaction between chlorine and isoprene yields a monochloride, 2-chloromethyl-1, 3-butadiene, and both 3, 4-dichloro-2-methyl-1-butene and 1, 4-dichloro-2-methyl-2-butene. These compounds are formed by 3, 4- and 1, 4-additions respectively.

The mechanistic implications of these reactions are discussed.

THE literature related to the addition of halogens to dienes is rather extensive. However, with the exception of the work of Mislow¹ and Hatch, Gardner and Gilbert² on the addition of bromine to butadiene and the work of Heasley, *et al.*³ on the addition of bromine to isoprene, much of the research on this important type of reaction is characterized by faulty identification of reaction products and a failure to evaluate the effects of allylic rearrangement. The more complex reaction between halogens and chloroprene (2-chloro-1,3-butadiene) has received little attention.

The addition of bromine to both isoprene and chloroprene affords the opportunity to contrast the influence of an electron releasing group (-CH₃) and an electron attracting group (-Cl) on the course of this reaction. From electronic considerations the reaction with isoprene should go more readily than with chloroprene and 1,2-, 3,4-, and 1,4-addition products would be formed. Petrov, however, reported⁴ only 3,4- and 1,4-addition compounds. He also noted the allylic rearrangement of the 3,4-addition product to the *cis* 1,4-addition product which in turn isomerized to the *trans* isomer. This is interesting because, from a consideration of eclipsing effects, the *trans* isomer should be the initial product³. It is the exclusive product with the allylic rearrangement of 3,4-dibromo-1-butene to 1,4-dibromo-2-butene.⁵

The formation of 2-bromomethyl-1,3-butadiene by the reaction between bromine and isoprene cannot

be discounted but it is unlikely because isobutylene reacts with bromine by addition.

Experimental

The various reaction mixtures were fractionated through a five-foot helix packed vacuum jacketed column. The fractions thus obtained were reduced by lithium aluminium hydride in tetrahydrofuran and analyzed by gas chromatography. The individual compounds were characterized by comparison with the retention time of authentic samples. The gas chromatographic equipment used for analysis consisted of a 10 ft × 1/4 in. copper column with either dinonyl phthalate or Curtin X₃ Universal Adsorbent on 40-60 mesh fire brick. The detector was a thermal conductivity cell. Infrared spectra were obtained on a Beckman IR 5 spectrophotometer.

Addition of Bromine to Chloroprene :

To a cold solution (0° to -5°) of chloroprene (307.0 g, 3.428 moles) in 500 ml of chloroform was added 276.8 g (1.732 moles) of bromine in 500 ml of chloroform. The addition was dropwise and the reacting mixture was vigorously stirred. After the reaction was complete the solvent was removed under reduced pressure at 30°. Fractionation of the 2-chlorodibromobutenes gave a 96% yield of 2-chloro-1,4-dibromo-2-butene. Physical data for this compound are in Table 1.

The reaction products from the lithium aluminium hydride reduction of 2-chloro-1,4-dibromo-2-butene were distilled into a cold trap and analysed by gas chromatography. The main product was *trans*-2-chloro-2-butene along with a small amount of the *cis* isomer.

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TABLE 1—SELECTED PHYSICAL PROPERTIES OF CERTAIN UNSATURATED HALO COMPOUNDS

Compound	Boiling point °C (Torr)		Index of refraction n_D^t		Density d_4	
	Found	Literature	Found	Literature	Found	Literature
2-Chloro-1,4-dibromo-2-butene	65(2.0)		1.5800(15) 1.5780(20) 1.5760(25)		2.0255(20) 2.0220(25)	
<i>trans</i> -1,4-Dibromo-2-methyl-2-butene	74–76(6)	48–49(0.1–0.2) ^a	1.5622(20) 1.5600(25)	1.5632(20) ^b	1.7965(20) 1.7905(25)	1.7960(20) ^b
2-Chloromethyl-1,3-butadiene	50(100)	50.4(100) ^c	1.4660(15) 1.4795(20)	1.4651(15) ^d 1.4792(20) ^c	0.949 (20) 0.884 (25) 0.841 (30)	0.955 (20) ^c
3,4-Dichloro-2-methyl-1-butene	60–61(50) ^a 143(760)	60(50) ^c 142–143.5(760) ^c	1.4676(20) 1.4642(25) 1.4623(30)	1.4712(20) ^b	1.1181(20) 1.1110(25) 1.1068(30)	1.1256(20) ^b
1,4-Dichloro-2-methyl-2-butene	56(10) 92–93(50)	56(10) ^c 93(50) ^c	1.4939(20) 1.4891(30)	1.4932(20) ^c	1.1520(20) 1.1479(25) 1.1427(30)	1.1526(20) ^c

^a Heasley, V. L., Frye, C. L., Gore, R. Y., and Wilday, P. S., *J. Org. Chem.*, 33(6), 2342 (1968).

^b Petrov, A. A., *J. Gen. Chem.*, (USSR), 13, 741 (1943).

^c Williams, H. G., and Jones, W. J. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 829.

^d Tishchenko, D. V., Abramova, A., and Yarzhen-skaya, E., *Zhur. Obshchei. Khim.*, 27, 227 (1957).

A solution (at 7°) of 41.3 g of 2-chloro-1,4-dibromo-2-butene in 400 ml of acetone was oxidized by 175.0 g of powdered potassium permanganate during vigorous stirring of the reaction mixture.¹³ The main oxidation product was bromoacetic acid, m.p. 49–50° (lit.¹⁴ 50°). This indicates that the bromination of chloroprene gave the 1,4-addition product.

Addition of Bromine to Isoprene:

The same procedure was used for the reaction between bromine (4.50 moles) and isoprene (3.91 moles) as was used for the reaction between bromine and chloroprene. Distillation of the reaction products gave only one major product, 90%, which was *trans*-1,4-dibromo-2-methyl-2-butene. Physical data for this compound are in Table 1.

The dibromomethylbutenes were reduced by lithium aluminium hydride and the major product was 2-methyl-2-butene with 2-methyl-1-butene and 3-methyl-1-butene as minor products.

The Reaction between Chlorine and Isoprene:

Chlorine (283 g, 4.00 moles) in one liter of carbon tetrachloride was added dropwise to a solution (–10°) of 272 g (4.00 moles) of isoprene in 750 ml of carbon tetrachloride. The reaction mixture was distilled under reduced pressure and three products were obtained: 2-chloromethyl-1,3-butadiene, 3,4-dichloro-2-methyl-1-butene, and 1,4-dichloro-2-methyl-2-butene. Gas chromatographic analysis of the reaction mixture indicated a product ratio of 28 to 9 to 29. Physical properties of these compounds are in Table 1.

2-Chloromethyl-1,3-butadiene was reduced by lithium aluminium hydride to give only isoprene; b.p. 33.5°–34° (lit.¹³ 34.1°); n_D^{20} 1.4210 (lit.¹³ 1.4216).

3,4-Dichloro-2-methyl-1-butene was reduced in a similar manner to give one major product: b.p. 33°–34°; n_D^{20} 1.4218. The gas chromatogram of this material was compared with authentic methylbutenes and with isoprene and it was shown that it was not possible to separate 2-methyl-2-butene and isoprene with the chromatographic column used because of the similarity of their retention times. 3,4-Dichloro-2-methyl-1-butene (4.0 g) dissolved in 30 ml of carbon tetrachloride was ozonized at –20°. A saturated solution of 5,5-dimethylcyclohexane-1,3-dione was used to trap the formaldehyde. A white precipitate was formed, m.p. 188°–189° (lit.¹⁴ 189°). This indicated the presence of a terminal double bond in the dichloro-2-methylbutene. The infrared spectrum of the ozonide product showed a strong carbonyl absorption at 5.8 μ which was identified by the iodoform test¹⁵ and gave iodoform: m.p. 118.5°–120° (lit.¹⁵ 119°–121°).

Lithium aluminium hydride reduction of 1,4-dichloro-2-methyl-2-butene gave only one product as indicated by gas chromatographic analysis. This product was 2-methyl-2-butene: b.p. 38° (lit.¹³ 38.5°); n_D^{20} 1.3890 (lit.¹³ 1.3874).

Results and Discussion

Addition of Bromine to Chloroprene:

The addition of bromine to chloroprene could give 3-chloro-3,4-dibromo-1-butene (by 1,2-addition), 2-chloro-3,4-dibromo-1-butene (by 3,4-addition) and *cis*- and *trans*-2-chloro-1,4-dibromo-2-butene (1,4-addition). The ratio of products is determined to a large extent by the initial bromine addition complex and, subsequently, by the transition state—

both 2-methyl-1-butene and 3-methyl-1-butene. No isoprene was present. These data confirm that the addition of bromine to isoprene goes by 1,2-, 3,4- and 1,4-addition with the major reaction being 1,4-addition.³ The ratio cannot be determined by lithium aluminium hydride reduction because both the 1,2- and 3,4-addition products will, on reduction, give at least some 2-methyl-2-butene. Distillation data confirmed the presence of the three methylbutenes and the absence of isoprene. The absence of isoprene indicates the absence of 2-bromomethyl-1,3-butadiene, the compound formed by bromine substitution on the methyl group of isoprene.

The 1,4-dibromo-2-methyl-2-butene was characterized by its physical properties and its infrared spectrum. The spectrum shows the absorption at 8.20μ ($-\overset{|}{\text{C}}=\overset{|}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_2\text{Br}$) and 8.39μ ($-\overset{|}{\text{C}}=\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2\text{Br}$). The carbon-carbon double bond stretching frequency at 6.18μ was weak as would be expected for a relatively symmetrically substituted double bond. It was not possible to assign geometrical configuration from either the infrared spectrum or from the lithium aluminium hydride reduction products. Heasley, *et al.*, report³ ca 10 to 1 ratio of *trans* to *cis* isomers under similar reaction conditions.

The information obtained from the addition of bromine to isoprene is equivocal because of the inability to make a quantitative estimate of the three isomers formed by this reaction. It was established, however, that there was both 1,2- and 3,4-addition as previously reported.³

The Reaction between Chlorine and Isoprene :

The reaction between chlorine and isoprene should yield both mono- and dichloro products. The monochloro compound should be an allylic chloride by analogy with the reaction between chlorine and isobutylene.

This reaction would lead to 1,2-addition if a proton had not been released by the methyl group, which requires a more or less formal positive charge on the tertiary carbon atom. It is generally accepted that a cyclic halonium complex is involved in the transition state during the second step of the addition reaction. If the allylic monochloride is formed it would be good evidence for at least some ion mechanism being operative.

The early literature on the reaction between chlorine and isoprene reported that the monochloride was 1-chloro-2-methyl-1,3-butadiene.⁸ After this investigation had been completed Tishchenko, Abramova and Yarzhen-skya reported⁹ that the

monochloride was 2-chloromethyl-1,3-butadiene. This is the same conclusion we had reached from the following evidence. The monochloride reacted with lithium aluminium hydride to give isoprene. A vinyl chloride would not react with this reagent under the conditions used.¹⁰ The infrared spectrum had the characteristic 7.95μ absorption of an allylic chloride of the following types⁶, $-\overset{|}{\text{C}}=\overset{|}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}$, and a diene absorption at 6.6μ .

The 3,4-addition product, 3,4-dichloro-2-methyl-1-butene, was characterized by elemental analysis ($\text{C}_5\text{H}_8\text{Cl}_2$), its density, index of refraction, and boiling point, all of which are within reasonable agreement with those reported in the literature⁸ (Table 1). The data obtained in this work are considered to be more accurate. The infrared spectrum has a fairly strong absorption at 6.20μ which indicates a terminal double bond. The broad band at 10.6μ may indicate

a disubstituted terminal double bond, $-\overset{|}{\text{C}}=\text{CH}_2$. The characteristic absorptions at either 7.94μ or 8.01μ of primary allylic chlorides were absent. The reduction with lithium aluminium hydride produced 2-methyl-2-butene. This is not negative evidence because similar compounds (3,4-dichloro-1-butene¹¹ and 2,3,3-trichloro-1-butene⁷) undergo allylic rearrangement during this reaction. Ozonolysis of the compound gave formaldehyde (a terminal double

bond) and a methyl carbonyl compound ($-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_3$). Thus, the following structure is indicated :

CH_3
 $-\overset{|}{\text{C}}=\overset{|}{\text{C}}-\overset{|}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_2$. Oxidation by potassium permanganate gave only one carbonyl compound which indicates a terminal carbon-carbon double bond and a

general structure of $-\overset{|}{\text{C}}-\overset{|}{\text{C}}-\overset{|}{\text{C}}=\text{CH}_2$.

The 1,4-addition product, 1,4-dichloro-2-methyl-2-butene, was characterized by elemental analysis $\text{C}_5\text{H}_8\text{Cl}_2$, and its index of refraction, density, and boiling point as reported in the literature⁸. The infrared spectrum has the characteristic absorption at 8.01μ ($-\overset{|}{\text{C}}=\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}$) and 7.94μ ($-\overset{|}{\text{C}}=\overset{|}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}$). The weak absorption at 6.14μ is characteristic of a relatively symmetrically substituted double bond. It is not possible to assign geometrical configuration from the spectrum other than suggest that if the compound had the *cis* configuration, the carbon-carbon stretching absorption would have been stronger.

An evaluation of the influence of the methyl group of isoprene on the distribution of the chlorine addition products (1,2-, 1,4- and 3,4-addition) is complicated by the fact that the intermediate for the 1,2-addition product causes a rejection of an allylic monochloride. The literature for this type of reaction has been summarized by Taft¹² and certain generalizations were made in respect to the ratio of

addition to substitution. The fact that the high percent of monochloride (27.7%) is indicative of an increased electron density of the carbon-carbon double bond caused by the presence of the methyl group. The formation of an allylic monochloride is strong evidence for an ionic transition state in the reaction between chlorine and isoprene.

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